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धन्योऽयं भारतो देशो धन्येयं सुरभारती ।
तदुपासकाः वयं धन्या अहो परम्परा ॥

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Poverty Narration in Pañcatantra: A Socio-cultural Study

Dr. Dharmendra Das

Poverty is one of the major concept accepted in curriculum of humanity and social science. It is a condition which is deprived of essentials that determine the quality of life. Poverty is analyzed in Sanskrit literature as social indicator like illiteracy level. Moral teaching through poverty narration is one of the poetic components of Sanskrit fable literature. In the light of socio-cultural investigation, the current study is a modest attempt to discuss about description of poverty as reflected in Sanskrit fable particularly in Pañcatantra.

Key words: Poverty, Fable, Sanskrit, Socio-cultural, *Pañcatantra*, Illiteracy

0.0 Introduction

The history of Indian culture may be taken to be the history of Sanskrit literature itself, which is quite ancient. If we want to know the history of our country, it is necessary for us to study the history of Sanskrit literature. Much before the alphabet had come into existence in the other countries of the world, India had already created its own world of literature. All this literature is in Sanskrit, which is one of the foremost languages of the world. Sanskrit literature is quite vast and, in many cases, unique. This literature still continues to be the moving force in shaping human values and ideas. The wealth of knowledge available in Sanskrit literature is quite limitless. The Vedic literature which possibly is the most extant literature in the world is in Sanskrit language. Literary works comparable to the best in the world is in Sanskrit language. Classics like the Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata, Bhāgavata, the Purāṇas, Subhṅṣitas are available in different literary

forms like prose, poetry, *champu*. In addition, source material on such subjects as Medicine, Astronomy, Architecture, Economics, Political Science, Mathematics, Music and very many other subjects are in Sanskrit. Sanskrit literature possesses invaluable wealth of knowledge. It inspires man to lead a successful life.

1.0 Relevance and scope of the present study

The fable as a narrative structure is one which is used to educate a fastidious lesson regarding deficiencies in the human character. It usually involves animals which have been imbibed with human characteristics. In Sanskrit literature, the origin of the fable is in some way connected to the *Upaniṣads*, where the relationship between man and animal is often emphasized. In today's world, the fable literature is an ideal platform to not only explore the connection between real life problems and literature but also to illustrate the relationship between humans and other life forms including animals.

Among such works is the "*Pañcatantra*" which is a famous fable in Sanskrit. The work has been translated into almost all languages of the world. Tradition ascribes the *Pañcatantra* to Viṣṇu Śarmā, whose existence has not been conclusively established. Viṣṇu Śarmā was apparently a celebrated teacher living in *Mahilāropya*. At the age of eighty, he undertook to educate three very refractory princes, in six months, in the art of governance. The stories he used as teaching aids form the *Pañcatantra*. The stories are divided into five '*tantras*', namely,

1. *Mitrabhedah* (Conflict amongst friends),
2. *Mitrasamprāptih* (Acquisition of friends),
3. *Kākolūkīyam* (War between crows and owls),
4. *Lavdhapraṇāśah* (The loss of profits),
5. *Aparīkṣitakārakam* (Action without due consideration).

The present study is about the poverty narration and its socio-cultural importance which can be composed from fifth part (tantra) of *Pañcatantra*.

2.0 General perception about poverty in Sanskrit literature

Regarding poverty we have the iconic story of Sudāmā. The protagonist is poor but the focus of the story is not Dickensian details but his other traits, his poverty is stated as a fact and there it ends. All narratives involve choice of words which themselves among the characters. In Indian context poverty is generally not seen as an affliction to be cured contrary to how it is perceived in the west.

Poverty narration is not so popular narration in Sanskrit literature. But, through a proper investigation may be noticed in the famous Sanskrit drama of Śūdraka's *Mṛcchakaṭikam*. According to dramatist Śūdraka, poverty in the sense may be understood as a condition in which a person or community is lacking in the basic needs for a minimum standard of well-being and life, particularly as a result of a persistent lack of income. Poverty may affect individuals or group, and it is not confined to the developing nations. Poverty in developed countries is manifested in a set of social problems. In this play, Cārudatta, the hero is leading a life of poverty. Everything is empty to a poor man. There are some verses collected here for references mentioned below

शून्यमपुत्रस्य गृहं चिरशून्यं नास्ति यस्य सन्मित्रम् ।
 मूर्खस्य दिशः शून्याः सर्वं शून्यं दरिद्रस्य ॥¹
 सुखं हि दुःखान्यनुभूय शोभते धनान्धकारेष्विव दीपदर्शनम् ।
 सुखात्तु यो याति नरो दरिद्रतां धृतः शरीरेण मृतः स जीवति ॥²
 दारिद्रयान्मरणाद्वा मरणं मम रोचते न दारिद्र्यम् ।
 अल्पक्लेशं मरणं दारिद्र्यमनन्तकं दुःखम् ॥³
 दरिद्रयाद्ध्ययमेति हीपरिगतः प्रभ्रश्यते तेजसो
 निस्तेजाः परिभूयते परिभवान्निर्वेदमापद्यते ॥
 निर्विण्णः शुचमेति शोकपिहितो बुद्ध्या परित्यज्यते
 निर्बुद्धिः क्षयमेत्यहो निर्धनता सर्वापदामास्पदम् ॥⁴

Similar kind of poverty narration in Sanskrit is noticed in Hitopadesa of Pandit Narayana. *Hitopadeśa* is a text consisting of fables with both animal and human characters. In the story of Muṣikaparibrājakakathā of *Hitopadeśa*, there is about moral teaching based on poverty narration as follows:

अपुत्रस्य गृहं शून्यं सन्मित्ररहितस्य च ।
 मूर्खस्य च दिशः शून्याः सर्वशून्या दरिद्रता ॥
 दारिद्रयान्मरणाद्वापि दारिद्र्यमवरं स्मृतम् ।
 अल्पक्लेशेन मरणं, दारिद्र्यमतिदुःसहम् ॥⁵

Poverty is not at all good for the society. One should be conscious to fight against the poverty. It is rightly said that the situation of death is far better than to face a situation of poverty. Poverty causes unending pain according to narration of *Hitopadeśa*. As the present study is on Sanskrit fable, *Hitopadeśa's* narration is decidedly meaningful in

the existence of a human being. The dramatic literature may be a source of poverty narration. Moral teaching through poverty narration is experienced in *Hitopadeśa*. *Pañcatantra* too have not lagged behind in this mission. So, the present investigation has taken the text of *Pañcatantra* to find out the socio-cultural importance of poverty narration.

3.0 Socio-cultural Significance of poverty narration in *Pañcatantra*

The concept 'culture' is defined as the sum total of social actions and achievements in different spheres. It is like a perennial river ever watching the performances, achievements, ability, diffidence, frailty and so on of human races. Like art, architecture and sculpture; literature and written records convey the messages of culture. Apart from fictional point of view *Pañcatantra* is very useful as throwing light on several aspects of social life. The poverty narrations found in *Pañcatantra* are nothing but the specimens of human speech-items committed sometimes in response mostly to specific behavioral impulses which are found neatly recorded in Sanskrit fable literature. The first story (The Barber) of fifth part of *Pañcatantra* is the source of poverty narration. Good disposition, purity of conduct, forbearance, kindness or politeness, sweetness of temper and birth in a noble family- all these make no difference when a man is without wealth:

शीलं शौचं क्षान्तिर्दाक्षिण्यं मधुरता कुले जन्म ।
न विराजन्ति हि सर्व वित्तहीनस्य पुरुषस्य ॥ 6

Similar type of poverty narration is found in *Nītiśatakaṁ* of *Bhartṛhari*. One who is wealthy is also considered as well born, learned, a man of information, a good judge of qualifications, an able speaker and a handsome person.⁷ Everything good is invariably dependent upon gold. According to the *Mahābhārata*, the Wise man of this world is rich ones.⁸ It is really wonderful that a man deprived of wealth instantly becomes quite a different and changed being, not with standing his being still the master of his former senses, actions, and the same bright intellect and power of speech.⁹ The following verses of *Pañcatantra* will clear both the aspects poverty and importance of wealth as well as attributes.

Self-respect vanity, worldly knowledge, grace, and beneficence - all these vanish simultaneously when a man is reduced to penury:

मानो वा दर्पा वा विज्ञानं विभ्रमः सुबुद्धिर्वा ।

सर्वं प्रणश्यति समं वित्तविहीनो यदा पुरुषः ॥¹⁰

Through the anxiety of supporting the family, the talent, even of the talented, daily and constantly declines like the beauty of *Sirisha* when struck by the gales of the spring:

प्रतिदिवसं याति लयं वसन्तवाताहातेव शिशिरश्रीः ।

बुद्धिर्बुद्धिमतामपि कुटुम्बभरचिन्तया सततम् ॥¹¹

The talented even of a very talented man, when his fortune declines, is lost by the constant anxiety of acquiring ghee (clarified butter), salt, oil, rice, clothing, and fuel for the support of his family:

नश्यति विपुलमतेरपि बुद्धिः पुरुषस्य मदविभवस्य ।

घृतलवणतैलनण्डुलवस्त्रेन्धनचिन्तया सततम् ॥¹²

The house of a poor man becomes or appears like the sky, the stars in which are invisible, like a dry lake and a terrible burial ground, and seems quite ugly through originally beautiful:

गगनमिव नष्टतारं शुष्कं सरः श्मशानमिव रौद्रम् ।

प्रियदर्शनमपि रुक्षं भवति गृहं धनविहीनस्य ॥¹³

The poor people though they live before the eyes of rich persons are not seen to exist as the bubbles of water that constantly rise on the surface and disappear:

न विभाव्यन्ते लघवो वित्तविहीनाः पुरोऽपि निवसन्तः ।

सततं जातविनष्टाः पयसामिव बुदबुदाः पयसि ॥¹⁴

Multitudes of people are always attached to a rich person though void of noble birth, virtue and good disposition, as if he were the wish-tree, after having left one who is nobly-born, clever and humane(if he be a poor):

सुकुलं कुशलं सुजनं विहाय कुलकुशलशीलविकलेऽपि ।

आद्ये कल्पतराविव नित्यं रज्यन्ति जननिवहाः ॥¹⁵

Also, there is no such importance in this world of a learned person without any wealth. Good actions done in the previous existence are of no use in this birth. Even learned men born in a noble family, become the slaves of a person when he possesses

wealth. Everything, virtue, glory, honour, things human and divine, all are slaves to riches. The God of this world is riches:

विकलमिहं पूर्वसुकृतं विद्यावन्तोऽपि कुलसमुदभूताः ।

यस्य यदा विभवः स्यात्तस्य तदा दासतां यान्ति ॥ 16

The above all statements are thoughts of a person who had lost his fortune. These thoughts are presented by the author of *Pañcatantra* in literary forms. Practically, the poverty narration may not be accepted in the modern society. But, somehow, we may be agree with the socio-cultural thinking behind the poverty narration available in the Fable literature like *Pañcatantra*. The person in this present world is very much affected by desire. As, it is said rightly that when a man grows old his hair wears out, his teeth fall off, his eyes become dim, and the ears become hard of hearing, but his desire alone becomes fresh:

जीर्यन्ते जीर्यतः केशा दन्ता जीर्यन्ति जीर्यतः.

चक्षुः क्षोत्रे च जीर्यते तृष्णैका तरुणायते ॥ 17

Dream narration is a psycho-cultural thought found in *Pañcatantra* is also significant. The dream seen by anxiety, afflicted by the passion of love and intoxicated, is of no use, that is, whatever is seen by such persons will never be realized:

व्यधितेन सशोकेन चिन्तग्रस्तेन जन्तुना ।

कामार्त्तनाथ मत्तेन दृष्टः स्वप्नो निरर्थकः ॥ 18

The third story (Four Young Friends) of fifth part of *Pañcatantra* is another source of poverty narration. In a certain town, there lived four young fellows, who were the sons of Brāhmins. They were very friendly with one another. But they were utterly destitute. So they met to decide what to do. "Curse this poverty", they said. It is so true what they say" :

वरं वनं व्याघ्रगजादिसेवितं जलेन हीनं बहुकण्टकावृत्तम् ।

तृणानि शय्या परिधानवल्कलं न बन्धुमध्ये धनहीनजीवितम् ॥ 19

Better to resort to a forest inhabited by tigers, wild elephants, without water and full of many thorns; it also better to have grass of one's bed and the barks of trees for wearing apparel, than living without wealth (in poverty) in the midst of one's relatives:

स्वामी द्द्वेषि सुसेवितोऽपि सहसा प्रोज्झन्ति सद्बान्धवा
 राजन्ते न गुणास्त्यजन्ति तनुजाः स्फारीभवन्त्यापदः ।
 भार्या साधुसुवंशजाऽपि भजते नो यान्ति मित्राणि च
 न्यायारोपितविक्रमाण्यपि नृणां येषां न हि स्याद्धनम् ॥²⁰

When persons are without wealth, their masters though well-served, hate them, their good relatives desert them all of a sudden, their virtues do not shine forth, their sons leave them off, their adversity is heightened, their wives, though born of good and noble families, do not serve them, and their friends, whose great courage is based on justice, go away. Another narration is that the glory and respect in this world is not possible to achieve without wealth. Even if a man is brave, handsome, well-formed, eloquent and however conversant he may be with the use of weapons and versed in sciences, does not obtain glory and respect in this world of mortals without the possession of wealth:

शूरः सुरूपः सुभगश्च वाग्मी शस्त्राणि शास्त्राणि विदांकरोतु ।
 अर्थं विना नैव यश्च मानं प्राप्नोति मर्त्योऽत्र मनुष्यलोके ॥²¹

And, it is strange that these sound organs, that very name, that unimpeded talent, that very speech and very men when deprived of the warmth of wealth, are changed in a moment:

तानीन्द्रियाण्यविकलानि तदेव नाम सा बुद्धिरप्रतिहता वचनं तदेव ।
 अर्थोष्मणा विरहितः पुरुषः स एव बाह्यः क्षणेन भवतीति विचित्रमेतत् ॥²²

Poverty is narrated as a well designed picture of fewness, the home of hostility for human being. The word 'poverty' can be taken as synonym of the word 'death' according to *Pañcatantra*.²³

Analysis of social aspects of poverty links conditions of scarcity to aspects of the distribution of resources and power in a society as well as recognizes that poverty may be a function of the diminished "capability" of people to live the kinds of lives they value. Viṣṇu Śarmā faced the challenge of educating three unlettered princes, to awaken their intelligence, Viṣṇu Śarmā evolved a unique pedagogy for his aim was to teach the princes how to think, not what to think and it was thus that these entertaining and edifying stories came to be composed. In this connection, poverty narration in the form

of story may be treated as a helpful implement for language teaching in ancient India.

Poverty narration in Sanskrit literature and contemporary literature are very different because in ancient India poverty was not looked down upon. In ancient times metaphysical orientation was always considered superior to material in Indian social dynamics. The present investigation is looking it from a modern and global perspective.

4.0 Conclusion

As it has been observed from the above Sanskrit verses that the poverty is usually an indicator used relate to the levels of income and consumption. But now poverty is looked through other social indicators like illiteracy level. It has been evident that the Illiteracy as a cause that leads to poverty. Poverty narration in *Pañcatantra* is basically presented to improve the illiteracy level of the princes. The purpose is to enlighten the minds of the illiterate princes. Sanskrit fables are based on moral teaching. In this connection, moral teaching through poverty narration of *Pañcatantra* is in fact significant. The utility of the poverty narration may be acknowledged as socio-cultural oriented.

The lack of engagement of students about learning is a noteworthy issue of present-day training, where *Pañcatantra* can come to help as a method in bringing these students again towards schools. *Pañcatantra* has a component of inspiration, good judgment, thoughts and consistent considering. A man, who has studied this moral text '*Nītiśāstra*' or listened to its precepts, will never be defeated. Not even by *Indra*, the lord of heaven.

अधीते य इदं नित्यं नीतिशास्त्रं शृणोति च ।

न पराभवमाप्नोति शक्रादपि कदाचन ॥²⁴

End Notes

1. The home of a sonless person is empty; he who has not a real friend finds all time empty; the quarters are empty to a fool; and everything is empty to a poor man. (Translation)–Kale, M.R., (1994), *The Mṛichchhakaṭika* of Śūdraka, Motilal Banarsidass Publishers Private Limited, Delhi, p-11
2. Verily happiness appears splendid (tastes pleasanter) after a person has experienced troubles, like the sight of a lamp when there has been pitchy darkness. But, when a man is reduced to penury after he has enjoyed luxury, he lives a dead man, existing only by keeping up his body.(Translation), Ibid, p-23

3. Out of (these two, viz.) poverty and death, I like death, but not poverty. Death causes short-lived pain, while poverty is (i.e. entails) unending misery. (Translation), Ibid, p.-23
4. From penury a person passes to (feels) shame; being overcome by shame, he loses, he loses his spirit; devoid of spirit he is slighted; being slighted, he feels dejected; full of dejection, he comes to be sorry; being smitten with sorrow, he is left by his reason; and destitute of reason, he perishes. Ah! Pennilessness is the abode of all sorts of misfortunes! (Translation), Ibid, p.25
5. See, Hitopadeśa (Mitrālabha), Mūṣikaparivrājākathā, Verse -131 and 140
6. *Pañcatantram*, Part-5 (*aparikṣitakārikam*), Verse -2
7. *Yasyāsti vittaṃ sa naraḥ kulīnaḥ sa paṇḍitaḥ sa śrutavāṅguṇajñāḥ. sa eva vaktā sa ca darśanīyaḥ sarve guṇāḥ kāñcanamāśrayanti. - Nītiśatakam of Bhartṛhari, Verse-41*
8. *Yasyārthāstya mitrāṇi yasyārthāstya bāndhavāḥ. yasyārthāḥ sa pumānilloke yasyārthāḥ sa ca paṇḍitaḥ- Mahābhārata, Śāntiparva-8/19*
9. *Tānīndriyāṇi sakalāni tadeva karma sā buddhirapratihatā vacanāni tadeva arthoṣmaṇā virahitaḥ puruṣaḥ sa eva tvanyaḥ kṣaṇena bhavatī vicitrametat.- Nītiśatakam of Bhartṛhari, Verse-40*
10. Nītiśatakam of Bhartṛhari, Verse-3
11. *ibid.*, Verse-4
12. *ibid.*, Verse-5
13. *ibid.*, Verse-6
14. *ibid.*, Verse -7
15. *Pañcatantram*, Part-5(*aparikṣitakārikam*)-Verse - 8
16. *ibid.*, Verse - 9
17. *ibid.*, Verse -16
18. *ibid.*, Verse-11
19. *ibid.*, Story-3, Verse - 23
20. *ibid.*, Verse - 24
21. *ibid.*, Verse-25
22. *ibid.*, Verse-26
23. *mūrtaṃ lāghavamevaitadapāyānāmidaṃ gṛham / Paryāyo maraṇasyāyaṃ nirdhanatvaṃ*

śarīriṇām // Mitrasamprāptiḥ, Verse-106

24. See the conclusion of *Pañcatantra kīśāmājika evaṁrājānitika daśā: aitiḥāsika adhyayana*, Sharma, Dr. Dharmendra (Ed.), p.218

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